

IDENTIFYING γ -H2AX FOCI IN DNA

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Abstract — Environmental factors and a wide variety of medications can harm DNA. Because of this, it is extremely difficult to comprehend and anticipate the effects of exposure to DNA-damaging chemicals in medication development and environmental health studies. Double-strand breaks of DNA induce γ H2AX foci, which have become the gold standard for double-strand break detection. Measurements of γ H2AX Currently, measuring the degree of Double-strand breaks repair and detecting IR-induced DNA damage using phosphorylation is the most accurate approach available. Therefore, Measurements of H2AX foci might be a potential method to track Double-strand breaks or Double-strand break healing in cancer patients receiving radiation or chemotherapy so that dose can be tailored. As a result of nuclear mishaps and exposure to environmental pollutants that might harm DNA, it's also feasible that H2AX readings could be utilised for radiation biodosimetry for nuclear power plant employees or the general public. There are many techniques to detect and measure γ H2AX foci, and other unsolved problems are discussed and a solution attempted is presented.

Keywords— Cell, DNA, γ -H2AX, Radiation, Charm Algorithm, Unsharp Masking

I. INTRODUCTION

The foundation of all living things are cells. There are many billions of cells in a human body. Cells develop, divide, and pass away in a systematic way. They provide the body with structure, take nutrients from meals and turn them into energy while carrying out certain tasks. Additionally, cells have the ability to replicate themselves and contain the DNA and other

genetic material that makes up the body. Cell biology is the field of research that focuses on cells [1].

The scientific field of cell biology investigates the physiological characteristics, structural elements, organelles they contain, interactions with their surroundings, life cycle, division, and demise of cells. Both the microscopic and molecular levels of this occur. Research in cell biology covers a wide range of multicellular species, including humans, plants, and sponges, as well as unicellular animals like bacteria and protozoa.

In our present research study we have focused on detecting cellular DNA damage. In the following subsections we will look at DNA, the causes of DNA damage, and the analysis of DNA damage.

What exactly is a DNA?

Deoxyribonucleic acid, commonly referred to as DNA, is a sophisticated molecule that houses all the data required to create and sustain an organism. DNA is present in every living thing's cells. Actually, nearly every cell in a multicellular creature possesses the entirety of the DNA required for that organism. A DNA molecule is a double helix. Its structure is as shown in Fig. 1 looks a lot like a twisted spiral ladder [2]. The sugar of one nucleotide (big molecule made up of smaller

units called nucleotides) is connected to the phosphate of the next, making up the sides of the ladder's sides. Many times, sugar and phosphate are described as the "backbone" of DNA. Adenine (A), guanine (G), cytosine (C), and thymine (T) are the four chemical bases that make up DNA (T). A with T and C with G make base pairs, which are units made up of two bases in DNA. A sugar and phosphate molecule are also joined to each base. The daughter cell will sustain DNA damage during replication, resulting in the creation of aberrant cells and, eventually, cancer, if the DNA damage is not discovered and repaired. If there is any break in the DNA structures, the cell will operate incorrectly.

Fig. 1: DNA Structure [1]

Why DNA Damages?

Exposure to radiation [3] from sources such X-rays, gamma rays, and radiation from nuclear reactors causes DNA damage. From very high energy (high frequency) radiations like X-rays and gamma rays to very low energy (low frequency) radiations like radio waves and microwaves, there is a spectrum of radiation.

Cell analysis for the detection of DNA damage DNA damage tests are examined as part of the planning process for medication therapy. Radiation and medicines are frequently used in cancer treatment. This therapy causes death of tumor cells but also induce damage of DNA, which are DNA double-strand breaks (DSBs). The limited therapeutic window and considerable population variation in DNA damage susceptibility present a challenge for radiation and chemotherapy, which can result in severe adverse effects and treatment-related mortality. Typically, radiation and chemotherapy are administered over a period of weeks to months and are scheduled for 13 weeks. As a result, a patient DNA damage test might be performed as part of the therapy planning. After the initial dosage of chemotherapy or radiation, the degree of DNA damage and the ability for DNA repair might be assessed to enable tailored dosing in the next

weeks of treatment. Following DSB induction, hundreds of phosphorylated H2AX molecules quickly form what is known as gamma H2AX foci or H2AX foci in the chromatin around the DSB site [4], as illustrated in Fig. 3.

Red arrows in Fig. 3(a) denote foci, which were present when radiation first began to impact the cell. The number of foci grows after a particular period of time when the cell is totally affected by radiation, as illustrated in Fig. 3. (b).

Individual foci are marked in Fig. 3(c) by red solid circles that were carefully inserted. A yellow circle in Fig. 3(c) that is enlarged in Fig. 3(d) designates a region where foci cells overlap.

Fig. 3: A case of the development of H2AX foci [5].

Applications of γ H2AX Detection:

Clinical applications for measuring H2AX phosphorylation as a marker of DNA damage exist. The primary clinical use of H2AX measurements is the monitoring of radio- and chemotherapy-induced DSB levels as indicators of treatment efficacy [5, 6] and in dose/planning estimation, as well as the evaluation of DNA repair efficiency to forecast potential tumour sensitivity or resistance to anticancer drugs that damage DNA. Cancer therapy toxicity may also be predicted by measuring the amounts of DSB caused by cancer treatment in normal cells. DNA damage results from exposure to endogenous or environmental mutagens, which then triggers the DNA damage response (DDR) cascade.

By causing cell death or replicative senescence, the DDR machinery functions as a "anti-cancer barrier" and inhibits or delays the growth of tumours. However, if only malignant cells are able to get over the cell growth restriction imposed by the DDR pathway, chronic DDR activation can occasionally result in their survival [7]. Since H2AX is the most sensitive of the active DDR components, they can be employed as cancer biomarkers. This is how measures of H2AX levels can aid in the early detection of precancerous lesions or cancer [8, 9]. Detecting the impacts of environmental contaminants (air, food, etc.) or monitoring DNA damage brought on by mutagenic compounds in the workplace, such as nurses delivering cancer medications, are

some more possible practical uses of H2AX. The use of H2AX detection is shown in Fig.4 [10].

Fig. 4: Applications of detecting the γ H2AX foci [10]

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Understanding the current level of knowledge in the area where this study was undertaken, as well as identifying important research groups, authors, and venues where this research was presented, were the two main objectives of our literature review. Reviewing various sources mentioned in the literature was part of the survey procedure.

Radiotherapeutic diagnosis and treatment using X-ray, CT, PET, and other radiation-emitting equipment has become essential in modern medicine. Diagnostic radiation doses are often much lower, ranging from 0.3 to 30 mGy [12], while the doses given to patients during radiotherapy typically vary from 1 to 50 Gy [11].

The quick identification of those exposed to dangerously high radiation doses during a radiological or nuclear event or accident is essential for early triage and medical treatment choices [13, 14]. Understanding cellular apoptosis and mutation, which can result in catastrophic disorders like cancer, requires research on cellular DNA damage. A single double-strand break (DSB) in the genome may be enough to alter the DNA and cause cancer or cell death [15].

DNA DSBs, which are one of the most harmful lesions to produce genomic changes and cancer at low levels and considerable morbidity at larger levels, are created as a result of radiation exposure. The discovery of phosphorylated H2AX foci (gammaH2AX or H2AX) at each rupture site, foci that may be seen by immunocyto and immunohistochemical methods, can be used to detect the existence of DSB [16].

The detection of H2AX foci produced by ionising radiation (IR) has been carried out using a variety of human materials, including lymphocytes, oral cells, and skin biopsies; summarised in [17].

Quantitative information can only be acquired with the currently known approaches after a lengthy wait of more than two days [18] and a high degree of technical competence. The scientific method made use of fluorescent dye-conjugated antibodies against phosphorylated histone H2AX.

A percentage of the sub-nuclear foci of H2AX [17] in nucleated blood cells, which indicate radiation-induced DNA double-strand breaks, survive for many days following radiation doses of 0.5 Gy or more [20]. Their occurrence increases linearly with radiation dosage. Through the detection of phosphorylated histone H2AX variations, the H2AX foci assay has recently developed into a very effective biodosimetry instrument that assesses DNA double-strand breaks (DSBs) indirectly [21, 22]. H2AX phosphorylation sensitivity to radiation and the speed of DNA strand breaks being repaired in irradiated cervical cancer cell lines [23].

While additional ways of DSB induction include phosphorylation mediated by the corresponding protein with Ataxia telangiectasia (ATR) or DNA-dependent protein kinase, the cellular machinery begins phosphorylating the H2AX residue Ser139 after the emergence of radiation-induced DSBs [22, 24]. The assessment of H2AX phosphorylation can therefore be used in clinical practise as a marker for premalignant lesions and to predict cell sensitivity to radiotherapy and chemotherapy [25]. Since this event is a signal to activate the DNA repair system, the H2AX foci assay has the potential to be used to detect DSBs that can result from radiation, genotoxic environmental toxins, drugs, and ageing as well as to measure DNA repair kinetics.

H2AX concentrations are determined using focus counting software from digital pictures or by hand counting in a fluorescence microscope. Both counting techniques are prone to errors, particularly at high IR dosages. Large and tiny foci can coexist side by side in the same nucleus, as shown in Fig. 5 by the white arrows. This is a typical problem with H2AX foci [26].

Fig. 5: Heterogeneous sizes of γ H2AX foci [26]

Additionally, as seen in Fig. 5 with the red arrow, foci that are adjacent to one another may be mistaken for a single huge focus. When counting is performed manually, the immunofluorescence microscopy approach is laborious due to the requirement to count foci in a significant number of nuclei in each sample. However, point finder software frequently counts foci that are different in size and brightness incorrectly because of issues with quantization settings. Finally, when employing digital systems, background staining from sample detritus might prevent counting. Focus counting microscopy technologies are now able to solve many of these issues, but [27].

These microscope systems are currently pricey and infrequently found in standard clinical labs.

The approach is nevertheless labor-intensive, time-consuming, and operator-dependent even if the quantification of H2AX foci is definitely sensitive enough to provide a valid determination of DSB induction in patients.

Furthermore, regular clinical laboratories rarely use automated fluorescence microscopes with automatic focus counting software. As a result, it is currently challenging to incorporate the H2AX foci approach into daily clinical practise. Numerous studies have been conducted, and some expensive, fully automated commercial systems are also available; these programmes even have certain drawbacks with relation to overlapping focus detection [28]. Particularly when ionising radiation is present in modest amounts, DNA damage is poorly understood. A sensitive method is also essential for identifying DNA damage following low-dose exposure [29, 30].

In [31], they created a technique for tracking chromosomal DSBs caused by incredibly low radiation doses that conducted quick, automated detection of radiation damage even at very low doses. The technique has to be extremely delicate as a result. Otherwise, radiation's impacts on cells would go undetected. Although 3D imaging and the extraction of useful information about foci are now made possible by digital cameras working in conjunction with zstage-enabled microscopes and deconvolution software [32], Edge information based 3D models and their limitations have been discussed [35], and the 3D labelling process is required to prevent counting the same focus more than once in the different layers of the zstack [36]. A novel in painting-based layered depth video for 3DTV has been proposed [33], and effective 3D depth map techniques are represented [34]. The WS method corrects tiny overlaps, but it misses situations of big overlaps [37]. Various techniques for converting 2D images to 3D images are provided in [38]. Stereoscopic camera handling with signal processing has been discussed [39].

Other study teams' focus analysis software tools [40] utilised the white top hat image processing and found foci with a structural element [41]. The focus is identified as being an object that is both smaller than the structuring element and brighter than its surrounds [42]. Foci size area varies from 0.2 micro meter² to 16 micro meter² [43]. Foci counting is very essential for dose estimation for treating the patient who has under gone the radiotherapy and chemotherapy [44].

III. FINDINGS FROM THE LITERATURE SURVEY

Some of the findings of our literature survey with regard to counting of γ H2AX foci are as follows.

- The manual counting of H2AX foci, which is a laborious, time-consuming, and error-prone procedure that necessitates a properly trained worker, is widely recognised and used in the majority of laboratories.
- Addressing the overlap of foci cells is one of the major research issues.
- Although there are some semi-automatic foci counting devices available, such as focus counters and cell profilers, each step of the process still requires human participation, and the technician using the system must have specific domain expertise.

- There is a lot of free software that is prone to errors due to overlapping foci and does not give consistent results across multiple counting iterations.
- There are also several commercial programmes for foci counting on the market, such as AKLIDES, etc. However, only up to 20% of the overlapping issues have been solved, and these commercial products are highly expensive.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

As per the observations made from the literature survey, we have seen that still there are many challenges in counting of γ H2AX foci. Considering these challenges, we want to develop a better solution. In this direction, we are presenting here our initial progress of work.

The proposed preliminary methodology developed for counting γ H2AX foci cell in the blood sample of a patient who is exposed for X-ray radiation is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig 6: Proposed Methodology of Foci Counting

A. Image Capturing and Slice Preparation

The blood sample of the patient is prepared on microscopic slide, the first step of our work is to acquire the image slices from the microscope through the prepared blood sample. The image was taken with a Nikon Eclipse 90i system microscope equipped with an epi-fluorescence attachment and image zoom lenses. Two Nikon CFI Plan Fluor air objective lenses, measuring 10X 0.30 NA and 40X 0.75 NA, were installed on the microscope. The Nikon 90i SDK for Windows (version 1.0.63.73) and the Nikon USB Eclipse-i Microscope driver, both of which are included in the iSeries Tools, are used to operate the microscope's Z axis (focus) (version 1.50). Based on the experienced lab technician suggestion, we have captured the focused images of the blood sample each at a successive depth of 10 micro meters of the blood sample. That is, first slice is obtained at the top of the sample, the second at the depth of 10 micro meters, the third at the depth of 20 micro meters and so on. We could obtain totally 24 slices from the prepared blood sample which is shown in Fig. 7. Once the image slices are captured the next step is to preprocess the individual slice of images using unsharp masking.

Fig 7: 24 Microscopic image slices captured on different depths from a patient blood sample

B. Image Preprocessing by Unsharp Masking

Unsharp masking is a well-known yet straightforward sharpening filter that enhances edges and other fine features by subtracting an unsharp (blurred) version of a picture from the original image. This filter is frequently applied in a variety of imaging areas to boost the apparent sharpness of a picture that is thought to be blurry. According to our process, an image's borders are first blurred using a Gaussian filter and then the original is removed. Instead of leaving it as that, the picture that was eliminated is multiplied by a weighting factor and then added to the original. This gives an image very similar to the original but with sharp edges dependent on the weight chosen. As per our observations, with weight less than 0.6 the lightly visible foci cells are lost. Whereas for above 0.7 weights we found that even the unwanted noise are visible in the images which further leads to conflicts on the expected result. So we have chosen the weight as 0.7. For a sample slice shown in Fig. 8(a), Fig. 8 (b) displays the final preprocessed slice picture.

Fig 8: (a) A sample Microscopic image

(b) Preprocessed image of slice of (a)

C. Charm Algorithm with Foci Count

The Compact Hough and Radial Map (Charm) algorithm is a Hough transform-based algorithm that is frequently used in medical image processing to extract various image parameters such as foci position, diameter, intensity, shape factor, and

distance to its nearest neighbour. It has broad applicability for the detection and analysis of cells.

We have used the Charm algorithm and extracted the said features of the image slices. These extracted parameters are then passed to another open-source program called "TRI2" (version 2.2). This program has been in use for various medical imaging purposes. It has batch processing capabilities. It applies image analysis and automatically classifies microscope images by cell count and cube type. The results are directly stored in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet.

Further we have used Data Analysis Plugin on generated Excel data for extracting the unique foci count.

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The results of foci count obtained for two different blood samples from our proposed methodology are tabulated in Table 1. For comparison and validation purpose we have obtained the foci count results from the traditional manual procedure also from an experienced lab technician from Life Science department of Manipal Institute of Technology, Manipal, India, for the same samples.

Table 1. Results of Foci Counts for Two Blood Samples

Process	Foci Count	
	Sample 1	Sample 2
Proposed Methodology	77	106
Traditional Manual Procedure	81	113

In comparison with the traditional manual procedure the results of the proposed methodology is 95.06% and 93.80%, respectively. By considering the results obtained for another set of 5 samples, the average accuracy is obtained as 94.96 %.

It has been observed that some of the image slices will have null information with no foci present in them. In our future work of development, we are planning to identify such image slices in the slice capturing stage only and not to include such slices for further processing, which improves the performance of the proposed system.

There is no set standard for how many slices should be generated for each cell picture, therefore preparing the slices of the cell image is crucial since the outcomes depend on it. This has to be looked into in our next work.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have presented the research study on the DNA double-strand breaks, induction of γ H2AX foci due to radiations and importance of its assessment to assess the DNA damage. We have reviewed the works reported in the literature for counting the γ H2AX foci and the need for an efficient system. In that direction of development of an efficient system, we have presented the development of our preliminary system of foci counting.

Result of our preliminary work of research is encouraging. Foci counts are nearer to counts of experienced lab technician and help to maintain some standardization for clinical purpose and for basic research. Further research is necessary for standardizing the slice depth. For more accuracy we can go for 3D technology and labeling methods.

We have attempted to overcome the overlapping of foci count by analyzing the data generated in Excel sheet. The overlapping is reduced by considering the statistical information like foci position, diameter and intensity of the foci. If any of these parameters are same in multiple slices then data of only one such cell is considered for counting foci avoiding multiple/duplicate counting. Presently this process is done manually by using data analyze plugin. In our future work we are planning to automate this process.

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